

OSMLanduse: A Dataset of European Union Land Use at 10 m Resolution Derived from OpenStreetMap and Sentinel-2

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Spatially resolved present-day land use is essential for climate-mitigation tracking, food-system monitoring, and spatial planning. Yet Europe still relies on CORINE Land Cover (CLC), a 100 m inventory updated on a six-year cycle that under-represents urban micro-mosaics [1]. In parallel, new 10 m land-cover products—ESA WorldCover and Google/WRI Dynamic World—excel at spectral separation but provide limited land-use semantics [2,3]. We aim to fuse OSM's human semantics with Sentinel-2's spatial grain to close this gap. The data is available at <https://doi.org/10.11588/data/IUTCDN> and the code here <https://github.com/schultzheidelberg/OpenStreetMap-land-use-for-Europe-2020>.

We present OSMLanduse, to our knowledge the first EU-wide 10 m land-use map that combines OpenStreetMap (OSM) with Sentinel-2 through a fully open workflow. Using the March 2020 OSM planet snapshot, we normalized tags into 13 CLC-compatible classes, directly labeling 61.8% of the EU28 (status as of March 2020). For unlabeled areas, we trained per-country residual convolutional neural networks on cloud-masked, multi-temporal Sentinel-2 medoid composites and mosaicked predictions with original OSM vectors into a seamless raster–vector hybrid. GeoTIFF tiles, training rasters, and the OSM→CLC translation table are openly released alongside code (GPL-3.0), trained weights, and a web viewer.

Map accuracy was assessed with 4,616 stratified reference points interpreted on sub-metre imagery. The product attains 89% overall accuracy (95% CI $\pm 2\%$); producer's accuracies range from 77% (shrub/herbaceous vegetation) to 99% (water bodies), with user's accuracies >93% for agricultural strata. Confusions arise primarily between spectrally similar urban green spaces and semi-natural grasslands, and between early construction sites and bare soil. An overview and a schematic of the processing pipeline are provided (see Figure 1).

Three methodological insights follow. First, the current density and thematic granularity of OSM land-use tags suffice to train deep networks that generalize across

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diverse biogeographic regions without external annotation campaigns [4]. Second, multi-temporal medoid compositing coupled with per-country models dampens atmospheric noise and phenological divergence, enabling continental consistency from uncalibrated top-of-atmosphere data. Third, open-science practices—public code, permissive licenses, trained weights, and cloud execution—place 10 m land-use mapping within reach of resource-constrained institutions [5].

Compute and reproducibility: The end-to-end continental training required 96 GPU-hours on commodity instances on FAO SEPAL; this is a one-off cost. Inference or fine-tuning on new regions is substantially cheaper. We release trained weights and per-country recipes so groups can (i) reuse weights as-is, (ii) fine-tune where OSM density allows, or (iii) run regional subsets. The pipeline is tile-based and linear in area; data-scarce regions can start with inference-only mapping and selectively fine-tune.

Update cadence: We will publish periodic updates by reusing weights and re-training only tiles with substantial OSM deltas, refreshing Sentinel-2 composites accordingly; the code already supports snapshot replacement. This addresses OSM temporal asynchrony and supports incorporation of community edits into future releases [6].

Applications and limitations: The dataset enables analyses from peri-urban sprawl quantification (SDG 11.3.1) to biodiversity sampling frames and downscaling of economic statistics. Limitations persist: crowdsourced tags are asynchronous; spectral ambiguity endures in arid shrublands and gravel pits; features <10 m (e.g., hedgerows) are sub-pixel. By releasing not only the map but all scripts, configs, and weights, we facilitate replication, auditing, regional adaptation, and incremental updates [6].

Figure 1. Overview of OSMlanduse (EU28, 10m, Mar 2020) and processing pipeline schematic (OSM tag harmonization, Sentinel-2 medoid compositing, per-country ResNet classification, raster–vector fusion).

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